

Compound dry-and-hot extremes exacerbate income inequality and poverty in Europe

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ABSTRACT

Heat waves and droughts are each highly damaging to people's incomes, but little is known of the joint impact on household welfare when these events occur simultaneously. We combine European household level survey data from 2004 to 2022 with high resolution temperature and drought data in a fixed effects econometric regression to investigate the change in household income and risk of poverty due to heat waves, droughts, and compound dry-and-hot extremes. We find that the average reduction in annual household income was 0.8 percentage points larger when heat waves coincided with a drought month, compared to when heat waves occurred alone. The compound climate impact was stronger for poorer households, with household in the poorest income quintile experiencing a reduction in average household income from the combined impacts of heatwave and drought of 2.7 percentage points larger than the households in the richest income quintile. We estimate that heat waves and droughts increased the at-risk-of-poverty (AROP) rate in Europe by 1.1 percentage points or an additional 5.6 million persons for 2004–2022 on average. Our projections indicate that limiting global warming to 1.5 °C by 2100 minimizes the negative impacts on income and limits the increase in income inequality and at-risk-of-poverty rates. Limiting warming also allows for more time to adapt to the adverse effects of heat waves and droughts. To reduce poverty by at least 15 million by 2030, the European Union has to scale up its protection of vulnerable populations through climate mitigation and adaptation.

1. Introduction

Heat waves and droughts are two extreme weather events that have direct and cascading impacts on human health, physical and natural capital. The experience of heat waves differs depending on its associated conditions, e.g., heat waves that coincide with extremely dry conditions, referred to as compound dry-and-hot extremes (CDHE), limit the options for recovering water that is lost through evapotranspiration and perspiration.¹

Due to the excessive strain on adaptive capacities, compound weather events, such as CDHE, are hypothesized to cause higher damages than the sum of its parts (Seneviratne et al., 2021). This implies that failure to account for these in impact modelling (e.g., see García-Leon et al., 2021 and Naumann et al., 2021 for macroeconomic impacts of heat and drought; Osberghaus and Abeling, 2022 for microeconomic impacts of heat) will likely lead to an underreporting of damages and an underestimation of sufficient adaptation measures. Scientific publications on the frequency of occurrence of compound weather events

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¹ At the other end of the spectrum are heat waves in extremely wet conditions, which we do not cover in this analysis due to low number of observations. We exclude these cases in the robustness check (i.e., including only heat waves during dry and normal conditions). The presence of water may signify more humid atmospheres – another compound extreme event – that limit the capacity of the human body to thermoregulate. Thermoregulation is the process by which the human body perspires to release excessive heat experienced by the body. The sweat produced during perspiration does not easily evaporate (and, therefore, not rapidly cool the body) during humid conditions.

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(Sedlmeier et al., 2018; Tripathy and Mishra, 2023; Suarez-Gutierrez et al., 2023) and the use of heat stress indicators (i.e., compound hot and humid events, wherein the human body fails to regulate internal temperatures through perspiration) to estimate health and productivity impacts (e.g., Lin et al., 2025; Orlov et al. 2020) have been increasing in the recent years. To our knowledge, there are no studies that quantify the impact of CDHE on household income, income inequality and poverty in Europe.

We aim to fill this knowledge gap on the impacts of CDHE on human welfare by answering four main research questions: (1) what is the difference in impact of joint heat waves and droughts (i.e., compound events) on household income compared to heat waves and droughts occurring separately (i.e., single events); (2) what is the difference in income impacts across geographical regions due to difference in the frequency of events; (3) given the same exposure to heat waves and droughts, are the income impacts the same across all income groups; and (4) what are the implications on poverty and at-risk-of-poverty (AROP) rate due to heat- and drought-related income impacts. We focus our analysis on Europe due to the rapid, unprecedented increase in frequency and exposure of subnational regions to droughts and extreme heat in the recent past, and the expected worsening of climate conditions in the future. Our estimation of the change in the AROP rate due to heat waves and droughts has a direct implication to achieving the European Pillar of Social Rights target of reducing poverty by 15 million by 2030 compared to 2019 (European Union, 2021).

To answer the four research questions, we combine household level income data from the EU SILC² with high frequency temperature data from ERA-5 and monthly drought indicator from the SPEIbase. We introduce a novel approach of disaggregating our heat wave indicator to those that occur during drought months, and those that do not; in order to compare compound vs single event impacts. Using the combined datasets, we apply a fixed effects econometric model to estimate the average impact on annual household income per heat wave day and per drought month. We apply the results of the econometric model to changes in the frequency of heat waves and droughts under three climate policy-relevant scenarios – 1.5 °C corresponding to Article 2 of the Paris Agreement (United Nations, 2015), 2 °C to compare the impacts of a half-a-degree increase in global mean temperatures, and 2.7 °C corresponding to the current climate policies (Climate Action Tracker, 2024).

We find that, on average from 2004 to 2022, annual household income was reduced by an additional 0.8 percentage points when heat waves coincided with a drought month, compared to when heat waves occurred alone. In the same period, the estimated reduction in average household income was 3.6 percentage points greater for the poorest income quintile compared to the richest income quintile. We estimate that heat waves and droughts have increased the at-risk-of-poverty (AROP) rate in Europe by 1.7 percent or about 303,900 persons per year. Our median projections show further reduction in annual household income by 21.6 percentage points and an increase in the AROP rate by 15.8 percentage points, if we do not meet the 1.5 °C warming limit by 2100.

We present in the next sections a review of relevant literature, the data and methods used in our analysis, followed by the results and discussions, and finally, our conclusions.

2. Literature review

In recent years, different parts of the world have been experiencing record-breaking heat waves and droughts. Once thought of as rare occurrences, Europe has already experienced multiple unprecedented high temperatures and prolonged periods of drought. Tripathy and Mishra (2023) estimated that the major CDHE event in 2022 was a once-in-over-

a-hundred-year event, with regional return periods of 354 years in Northern Italy, 420 years for the Iberian Peninsula, and 280 years in western parts of France. The European Environment Agency (2024) labelled 2023 as the warmest year on record, with Europe warming twice as fast as the global rate. Climate projections show that heat waves, droughts, and CDHE will likely increase in magnitude and duration in the future (Sedlmeier et al., 2018; Seneviratne et al., 2021; Yin et al., 2023). Europe could experience unprecedented magnitudes of CDHE in the future, such that heat stress levels that were expected to occur towards the end of the century are twice as likely to already happen in 2030 (Suarez-Gutierrez et al., 2023). The increases in magnitude and shorter return periods of high intensity heat waves and droughts can be attributed to rapid global warming. Because of warmer weather, low levels of snowfall during the winter months as well as persistently scarce rainfall up to the summer months lead to a higher likelihood of having dry summers (Copernicus Climate Change Service, 2023). Water scarcity is even more intensified by hotter summers and the higher rate of evapotranspiration. The short-run effects of warmer weathers, together with the decades-long preconditions of warmer North Atlantic sea-surface temperatures in Europe make it more likely that CDHE happens for years in close succession (Suarez-Gutierrez et al., 2023).

Heat waves and droughts are two of the most damaging extreme weather events in Europe (European Environment Agency, 2024). The damages from heat waves alone are estimated at 0.3–0.5 percent of European Gross Domestic Product (GDP), with GDP losses exceeding 1 percent in vulnerable regions (García-León et al., 2021). Agriculture, energy, and transportation are key production sectors directly affected by heat waves and droughts. Widespread crop failures result from low soil moisture and ground water availability, while prolonged impacts are caused by lower water reservoirs available for irrigation. Dry conditions coupled with hot temperatures are conducive conditions to the proliferation of pests and diseases that cause further reductions in crop yields. The estimated decrease in annual yields due to droughts alone is 10 percent compared to expected yields (Rossi et al., 2023); and more than 60 percent of agricultural losses are drought-related losses (Devot et al., 2023; Naumann et al., 2021). Low levels of rainfall and water available in reservoirs and rivers affect both hydropower generation, as well as nuclear power and other thermal power generation, which requires cooling water (European Commission, 2022; Rossi et al., 2023). Similarly, low levels of water in waterways used for transport impose limitations on the quantity of final and intermediate goods delivered (Rossi et al., 2023). The marginal impact of a heat wave day on individual earnings in Europe is estimated to be the largest for the Agriculture and Fisheries sector, followed by Wholesale and Retail Trade, and the least affected to be Financial, Real Estate and Business sector (Valenti and Vona, 2025).

It is well established that heat waves and droughts have severe effects on human health, including mortality, worsening of cardiovascular, kidney and respiratory diseases, heat stroke, and water-related diseases due to the increased concentration of pollutants during droughts (WHO, 2021; European Commission, 2022; Parsons, 2002; Heal and Park, 2013; Zhao et al., 2021). The 2022 CDHE alone has been estimated to have caused over 60,000 premature deaths in Europe (European Environment Agency, 2024; Toreti et al., 2022). Given current adaptation measures and the acceleration of summer mean temperatures in Europe by 0.142 °C per year between 2013 and 2022, Ballester et al. (2023) estimate an increase in heat-related mortality to 68,116 deaths each summer by 2030, 94,363 by 2040 and 120,610 by 2050; wherein heat-related mortality rate for women is estimated to be 63 percent higher compared to men, and higher for older population groups. Vicedo-Cabrera et al. (2021) attribute 37 percent of heat-related deaths during warm seasons to anthropogenic climate change. Deteriorated human conditions are often reflected in terms of losses in hours worked – either due to heat stress-related disabilities or because people work at a slower pace and take more health breaks (ILO, 2019; Heal and

² European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions.

Park, 2013; Kjellstrom et al., 2009; Parsons, 2002; Parsons, 2019). In Austria, heat-related losses in labour productivity lead to large reductions in gross value added of sectors that involve heavy work load outdoors, particularly Mining and Quarrying (− 6.5 percent), Manufacturing (−3.5 percent), Forestry and Logging (−3.2 percent) and Agriculture (−2.3 percent) (Kimmich et al., 2025).

On top of these cascading impacts from either droughts or heat waves, CDHE create a conducive environment for a third destructive event: wildfires. The 2023 wildfires across Europe resulted in 504 thousand hectares of burnt land and produced approximately 20 megatonnes (Mt) of CO₂ emissions (36). The estimate for 2022 surpassed 800 thousand hectares of burnt land (EFFIS, 2024; San-Miguel-Ayanz et al., 2024). Increases in the rate of premature human deaths correlate with increased exposure to health-damaging fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) from wildfires (Chowdhury et al., 2024).

Even with the same atmospheric conditions within a subnational region, exposure may still vary within-region, where real estate in high-risk areas (e.g., those that have fewer green spaces to protect from extreme heat, areas that are difficult to reach and have limited access to water supply) tend to be cheaper. These areas cater largely to families who cannot afford better housing options, such as poor households. Poor households, therefore, are more likely to live in high-exposure areas; and are more vulnerable to negative impacts due to the larger share of damages relative to total assets compared to richer households (Hallegatte et al., 2020). Poor households also have limited financial resources, networks, and access to markets (Hallegatte et al., 2020) and are faced with unequal costs in obtaining basic services and financial resources (Gutiérrez-Nieto et al., 2017) to cope and recover, therefore making them less capable of adapting to income shocks compared to richer households (Osberghaus and Abeling, 2022). Additional supply costs that firms take, such as investment costs to improve water supply during dry periods, are also passed on to consumers, which affect water affordability for poorer households (Rachunok and Fletcher, 2023). With every income shock, poor households have fewer resources and fewer options to avoid future impacts, thereby turning short-term impacts into long-term effects and pushing them into a poverty trap (Carter et al., 2007).

3. Data

We estimate the impact of heat waves and droughts on household income in NUTS-1 regions in Europe using a combination of household survey data and high-resolution reanalysis weather data from 2004 – 2022.

3.1. Household survey data

We source our household data from the EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC). The EU-SILC is a harmonised cross-sectional and longitudinal survey dataset that contains household and individual responses on income, poverty, social exclusion, and living conditions; and is based on representative probability samples of the population. The longitudinal data of the EU-SILC have a rotating sample design of mostly 4 years,³ i.e., in each year, a subsample of households is dropped and replaced by a new sample, and any subsample is interviewed for a maximum of 4 consecutive years (Wirth and Pforr, 2022). The EU-SILC has a spatial disaggregation of up to the NUTS-1 level. The availability of the EU-SILC data by country and year is presented in Annex 1 of this document.

The main dependent variable in our econometric analysis is the equivalised disposable household income (HX090).⁴ The equivalised disposable income⁵ is the household size-weighted, total annual household income after social transfers⁶ and tax deductions. The household size weights are based on the modified OECD scale, which assigns a weight of 1.0 for the first adult, 0.5 any other household members with ages equal and above 14 years, and 0.3 for any household member below 14 years old. The reference period of income variables is the last fixed 12-month period, e.g., the previous calendar or tax year. Income data is collected through varying methods and sources: collected via survey/interview, collected from administrative data, deductive/logical imputation, gross/net conversion, model-based imputation, or donor imputation.

The *i*hs transformation allows us to approximate a natural logarithmic function without dropping any zero or negative values, while still applying the same logarithmic rules for the interpretation of the coefficients for large numbers. The *i*hs transformation (also *arcsinh* or *asinh* function) has been widely used and referred to as an alternative to the log transformation by papers such Johnson (1949), Burbridge et al. (1988), Carboni (2012), Ravallion (2017), Bellemare and Wichman (2019), Norton (2022), Mullahy and Norton (2023), McKenzie (2023), Chen and Roth (2024). A comparison of the *i*hs results against a natural logarithm transformation is provided in Annex A.3.1.

The equivalised disposable household income is also used to determine the income quintile of the household, which we exploit to quantify the inequality in the distribution of heat waves and drought impacts. The same variable is used to calculate the AROP threshold and rate. We make use of income quintile-specific income impacts to calculate the change in AROP rates and population due to the exposure to heat waves and droughts.

Poverty in Europe is calculated using the “At-Risk-of-Poverty and social exclusion” (AROP) metric, comprised of three components: (1) the “at-risk-of-poverty” component that is based on income (household income less than the relative poverty threshold), (2) severe material and social deprivation that is based on social interactions and basic material ownership (affirmative to 7 of 13 questions to be “deprived”), and (3) work intensity based on the share of actual to potential hours worked (less than 20 % of potential hours worked to have low work intensity). A household is considered at-risk-of-poverty if it is considered “poor” in at least one of these components. In this analysis, we focus only on the first component, given the stronger evidence on the relationship between heatwaves and droughts on income as discussed in Section 2, compared to the other two components (e.g., social deprivation also considers frequency of visits to family and friends; and work intensity is influenced by other non-climatic factors, such as child care (EUROSTAT (c) (2025) and labour market slack). Our estimates of poverty incidence in this analysis are solely based on the income component.

The At-Risk-of-Poverty (AROP) metric “does not measure wealth or poverty, but low income in comparison to other residents in that country, which does not necessarily imply a low standard of living” (EUROSTAT (b) (2024)). It uses a relative poverty threshold (AROP60 threshold) to determine if a household is at-risk-of-poverty. The AROP60 threshold is calculated by taking 60 % of the country- and year-specific median equivalised income. Households whose income fall below this threshold are considered at-risk-of-poverty. We have created our own R script to accomplish the same computations made in the Stata do-file of Lange et al. (2021), which uses the EU-SILC cross-sectional data and the personal cross-sectional weights (RB050) to calculate the

⁴ HX090 is available from 2007 to 2021. In the absence of an indicator for the head of household, the HX090 value and other person-specific control variables used in the regression are taken from the response of the household member with the highest educational attainment.

⁵ See [Description of Target Variables EU SILC 2021](#).

⁶ Social transfers include.

³ For some countries, the rotating panel is for a period of 6 years.

nationally-representative at-risk-of-poverty threshold by country and year.⁷

Given the relative nature of the AROP60 threshold, the absolute poverty threshold differs by year and country, depending on the changes in the household income and the income distribution. We note that the relative threshold approach has been criticised due to the large dependency of the AROP rate to the distribution of income rather than purchasing power of households, and the comparability across different countries. For instance, because the AROP threshold is not tied to a measure of purchasing power that can be directly compared to a minimum living standard, countries that have increased (or decreased) in purchasing power have counterintuitive movements in the AROP rate (see [Jenkins, 2020](#); [Whelan and Maître, 2008](#)); or that poorer countries have lower AROP rates than richer countries (see [Goedemé et al., 2018](#)).

To balance out this criticism, we have taken the fixed poverty threshold from [Goedemé et al. \(2022\)](#), which statistically derived the country-specific minimum income required to cover for basic food and housing for a family of 2 adults and 2 children at 2017 EUR prices. To make this comparable with the derived AROP rate in our analysis, we, first, convert the estimated fixed poverty threshold to current prices using country-specific consumer price index, and then apply the OECD modified equivalence scale counting 1 for the first adult, 0.5 for the 2nd adult, and 0.3 for each of the children.

In addition to the equivalised disposable income, we also use the following variables from the EU SILC longitudinal dataset as control variables: the highest educational attainment in the household⁸ (PE040, PE041),⁹ gender of the household member with the highest educational attainment (RB090), age (RB010 minus RB080),¹⁰ and degree of urbanisation (DB100). Education data is summarised into nine aggregated categories: 0 = no education, 1 = primary, 2 = lower secondary, 3 = upper secondary, 4 = post-secondary, non-tertiary, 5 = tertiary, 6 = bachelors, 7 = masters, 8 = doctoral. The age of the respondent is the difference between the year of the last panel interview to the year of birth, and is categorised into three: 1 = below 18 years old, 2 = 18–64 years old, 3 = 65 years old and above. The degree of urbanisation is summarised to a binary indicator: 0 = rural area, 1 = cities or towns.

From a total of 9,595,477 individual-level observations from 2004 to 2022, we drop those without information on the NUTS 1 region (964,513 individual-level observations), except for countries whose NUTS 1 region is also the entire country.

As noted by [Eiffe and Till \(2014\)](#), many publications have made use only of portions of the EU-SILC due to its complexity, and therefore have not maximised the use of the entire EU-SILC longitudinal datasets (12). Following the documentation and Stata codes from [Mack \(2016\)](#), [Borst \(2018\)](#) and [Borst and Wirth \(2022\)](#), we combine all EU-SILC longitudinal data sets from 2004 to 2022 using the open-source programming software R. With the use of selected indicators in the EU-SILC and their availability in years and countries, the total number of observations utilised in the regression analysis is 3,872,331 households from 103 NUTS-1 regions across 31 European countries.¹¹

⁷ See [Adding Information on AROP thresholds to longitudinal EU-SILC data](#) for the Stata do-file and the documentation.

⁸ We use the educational attainment as a proxy for identifying the head of household.

⁹ The EU SILC variable for the highest educational attainment was PE040 from 2007 to 2020. It was renamed to PE041 in 2021.

¹⁰ Year of the interview minus year of birth.

¹¹ The number of observations is largely reduced from the merged EU-SILC longitudinal dataset because of two things: (1) only 1 person response per household is considered, (2) not all years for all countries have data on the equivalised disposable income and other control variables.

3.2. Weather and climate data

Our main independent variables to represent extreme heat and drought are the climatological heat waves and the Standardised Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI).

We source our historical heat waves data from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), Climate Data Store (CDS) (2024),¹² which uses the ERA5 hourly data on single levels from 1940 to 2022 to calculate the number of climatological heat wave days. A climatological heat wave is defined as a period of at least three consecutive days exceeding the 99th percentile of the daily maximum temperatures of the May to September season in the reference period 1971–2000, for the respective region. The relative threshold used in the heat wave indicator takes the differences in normal, local climate conditions into account. The gridded heat wave days are aggregated to the NUTS-1 level (area-weighted) and yearly values (total number of heat wave days in a year) to match the EU-SILC spatial and temporal resolutions. We chose this heat wave definition due to the relative threshold that takes the differences in normal, local climate conditions into account, and the simplicity in its calculation. Alternative heat stress indicators combine temperature with other factors such as wind and humidity (e.g., Wet Bulb Globe Temperature, Universal Thermal Climate Index); but because these are represented by indices that aggregate the different variable values, these do not allow us to clearly disaggregate between a hot event, a hot-and-dry event or a hot-and-humid event. The other alternative is to use absolute thresholds; however, these will exclude colder countries from being affected by heat waves, despite a sudden, significant deviation of temperature from region-specific average. Due to these disadvantages, we only use these alternative indicators for robustness checks.

As a robustness check, we have used alternative heat wave indicators: (1) the “number of hot days” which has an absolute threshold of 30 °C, 35 °C, and 40 °C maximum daily temperature, and (2) the “number of days that the Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) is above 32 °C”. UTCI is an equivalent temperature measurement in degrees Celsius; however, it is based on air temperature, relative humidity, wind speed and mean radiant temperature, and takes into consideration adaptation measures of the population (e.g., clothing depending on the outdoor temperature) ([C3S \(2024\)](#)).

The SPEI is a normalised measure of water balance over a specific time scale between the amount of water gained through precipitation and the amount of water lost through evapotranspiration over the time scale considered. We use a 6-month time scale or the cumulative water balance from the past 6 months to the present month (SPEI-06). We use SPEI-06 due to the temporally compounding nature of droughts, i.e., a summer drought can build up from low snowfall or rainfall from the preceding winter or spring ([C3S \(2023\)](#)). Following the literature, we define a drought month when the SPEI-06 has a value of less than -1.5 (severe dry) ([Beguería et al., 2014](#)). The SPEI-06 is sourced from SPEI-base v2.10 ([Beguería et al., 2024](#); [Vicente-Serrano et al., 2010](#)), which uses the FAO-56 Penman-Monteith estimation of potential evapotranspiration. The gridded SPEI data are aggregated to the NUTS-1 level (area-weighted) and yearly values (total number of dry months) to match the EU-SILC spatial resolutions.

Our temporal specification of the drought indicator assumes larger effects on income as the duration increases, regardless of how severe the drought is (i.e., a month of SPEI value of -3 will have the same estimated impact as a month of SPEI value of -1.6). This specification accounts for multiple dry events as opposed to only taking only the most severe drought event in the year (max SPEI value per year). However, we

¹² Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), Climate Data Store (CDS), (2024): Climate indicators for Europe from 1940 to 2100 derived from reanalysis and climate projections, Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store (CDS). (Accessed on 01-SEP-2024).

note some limitations to this approach. We assume no seasonality effects, such that the effect of a drought month on income is the same, regardless of when in the year it happens. This may not hold true for more specific analyses, e.g., crop-specific impact analyses where the stages of growth of the plants vis-à-vis when the drought months happen are critical to consider. Given the general scope of our analysis, we are unable to determine the critical months when droughts would have the largest impact. Considering the general, non-sector-specific scope of our analysis, we spatially aggregated the gridded data to the NUTS-1 level based on area weights to have a neutral stance on both labor- and capital-intensive livelihoods (e.g., droughts may be more relevant for farming livelihoods or areas with water transport with less population, while heatwaves may be relevant for both populated areas through labor productivity impacts, and less populated areas through destruction of crops and physical assets (i.e., heat limits of plants and infrastructure such as roads and buildings).

Similar to [Tripathy and Mishra \(2023\)](#), we define a CDHE event as the simultaneous occurrence of heat waves and droughts in the same month. To this end, we disaggregate the heat wave days indicator into heat wave-dry days (referring to CDHE days) and heat wave-non dry days (referring to heat waves during normal to wet conditions). For the robustness check, we also disaggregate the heat wave-non dry days to heat wave-normal days (heat wave with SPEI-06 values between -1.5 and 1.5) and heat wave-wet days (heat wave with SPEI-06 values above 1.5).

We calculated monthly projections of heat wave days and SPEI-06 using bias-corrected Global Climate Models (GCMs) from Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP2) under a future warming scenario, i.e., Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) 8.5. Using RCP 8.5, we identify the progression in global warming levels (up to 0.1 °C) for each of the GCMs: GFDL-ESM2M, HADGEM2-ES, IPSL-CM5A-LR, and MIROC5. This methodology allows us to include the Paris Agreement-consistent warming limit of well-below 2 °C (i.e., +1.5 °C by 2100 compared to the preindustrial period, compared to half-a-degree higher warming of + 2 °C) by identifying the year under RCP 8.5 when the global warming level (GWL) reaches 1.5 °C and 2 °C (see [Mitchell et al., 2017](#) for the methodology, and [Taylor et al., 2012](#) for the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5) where the ISIMIP2 calculations are based on). The same methodology is applied to derive the values of climate indicators following the current policy-relevant scenario (+2.7 °C by 2100 compared to the preindustrial period), wherein there is no change in climate mitigation action (see Climate Action [Tracker, 2024](#)). The climate projections are presented as changes relative to a reference period (GWL + 0.8 to + 1.4, depending on the GCM). We have selected 31 years around 2008 (1993–2023) as the reference period due to the overlap with our historical data (2004–2022), and the closeness to current warming levels (+1.3 °C in 2023 according to the Climate Action Tracker¹³).

We selected RCP 8.5 as opposed to other RCPs due to the range of global warming levels it covers, particularly up to GWL + 2.7. We present the GWLs under RCP 8.5 and the year that they are reached in each of the GCMs in Annex 2. We also show the years when the GCMs reach the GWLs + 1.5 °C, 2.0 °C, 3.0 °C and 4.0 °C by RCP in Annex 3, where only RCP8.5 covers the full range of scenarios (GWL reaching at least + 3.0 °C relative to pre-industrial period) in 4 GCMs. We note some assumptions and limitations in the use of RCP8.5 and our time-slicing method: (a) we assume that the corresponding change in our climate variables (i.e., HWdry, HWnondry, DD) for every 0.1 °C increment in GWLs does not vary largely across the different RCPs, and (b) we are not able to account for overshoot scenarios where the effect of a + 1.5 °C at 2100 is the same, regardless of the peak GWL from current years up to the end of the century.

¹³ <https://climateactiontracker.org/global/cat-thermometer/>. Accessed on October 9, 2025.

Table 1
Summary statistics, 2004–2022.

Table 1a: Continuous variables				
Variable name	Mean	Min	Max	SD
Equivalised household income	17,339.0	-1,299,790.0	6,178,830.0	20,765.8
Heatwave days	1.7	0.0	14.5	2.6
Heatwave dry days	0.5	0.0	13.9	1.7
Heatwave non-dry days	1.2	0.0	14.5	2.1
Drought months	1.2	0.0	11.0	2.1

Table 1b: Categorical Variables			
Variable name	Value	Frequency	Share to Total Obs
Age: below 18	1	6,007	0.1%
Age: 18–64	2	2,872,082	69.3%
Age: 65 and up	3	1,265,041	30.5%
Education: none	0	46,774	1.1%
Education: primary	1	332,858	8.0%
Education: lower secondary	2	485,419	11.7%
Education: upper secondary	3	1,615,925	39.0%
Education: post-secondary	4	173,433	4.2%
Education: tertiary	5	1,331,206	32.1%
Education: bachelors	6	14,944	0.4%
Education: masters	7	37,997	0.9%
Education: doctoral	8	1,879	0.0%
Education: NA		102,695	2.5%
Gender: male	1	2,126,808	51.3%
Gender: female	2	2,015,707	48.7%
Gender: NA		615	0.0%
Urban: no (rural)	0	1,407,462	34.0%
Urban: yes (cities or towns)	1	2,735,668	66.0%

Table 1c: EU-SILC Rotating Panel				
Variable name	Mean years	Min years	Max years	N
Unique household ID	3.2	1	19	1,272,522

In estimating the number of people at-risk-of-poverty in the future, we used the population projections from EUROPOP2023 ([EUROSTAT \(a\) \(2024\)](#)) for climate scenario-relevant years 2030 (for 1.5 °C representing current policy scenario) and 2100.¹⁴ The EUROPOP2023 does not have population information on Serbia and the UK. To fill in for this missing information, we extrapolated the population in 2022 and 2100 for the two countries using their historical population information, and applied an annual population growth rate of 0.5 % and 0.6 %, respectively. [Table 1](#) presents the summary statistics of the household and weather data used in this analysis.

4. Methods

4.1. Income impacts

We use a fixed-effects panel regression model on an unbalanced panel data using two equations: (1) the aggregate regression equation, where we use all observations, and (2) the distributional regression equation where we disaggregate the observations by income quintile, and run the same regression to estimate income quintile-specific coefficients:

Equation 1: Aggregate Regression Equation

$$ih(y_{it}) = \alpha + \beta_1 HWdry_{rt} + \beta_2 HWnondry_{rt} + \beta_3 DD_{rt} + \beta_c C_{it} + \mu_i + \gamma_t + \epsilon_{it}$$

Equation 2: Distributional Regression Equation

$$ih(y_{itq}) = \alpha + \beta_{1q} HWdry_{rt} + \beta_{2q} HWnondry_{rt} + \beta_{3q} DD_{rt} + \beta_{cq} C_{it} + \mu_{iq} + \gamma_t + \epsilon_{itq}$$

¹⁴ Source: Eurostat. Accessed on 23 October 2024.

$ihs(y_{itq})$ is the inverse hyperbolic sine of the equivalised disposable income for each household i , year t , and income quintile q .

β_{1q} is the estimated coefficient representing the response of y_q to changes in the number of heat wave days during dry months (*HWdry*) in NUTS-1 region r and year t .

β_{2q} is the estimated coefficient representing the response of y_q to changes in the number of heat wave days during normal to wet conditions (*HWnondry*) in NUTS-1 region r and year t .

β_{3q} is the estimated coefficient representing the response of y to changes in the drought duration or the number of drought months in a year (*DD*) in NUTS-1 region r and year t .

β_{cq} is a conformable vector of coefficients corresponding to the control variables (C): education, gender, age, and degree of urbanisation.

μ_{iq} represent the household fixed effects to control for time-invariant, household-specific characteristics. γ_t represent the year fixed effects, and ϵ_{itq} is the idiosyncratic error term.

To estimate the counterfactual effect of historical heatwaves and droughts, we multiply the regression coefficients (point estimate and a range of 95 % confidence interval) to the average annual values of *HWdry*, *HWnondry*, and *DD* from 2004 to 2022 by NUTS-1 region.

To estimate the future impacts to income, we multiply the regression coefficients (point estimate and a range of 95 % confidence interval) to the change in the values of *HWdry*, *HWnondry*, and *DD* under GWLs + 1.5 °C, +2.0 °C, + 2.7 °C at 2100 relative to a reference period (30-year average around 2008).

The results of the income impacts are all in percentage points: percent reduction in income with and without heatwaves nor droughts in the counterfactual effect, and the percent difference in income reduction in the different climate projections relative to the reference period.

4.2. Poverty implications

We derive the implications of heatwaves, droughts and CDHE on poverty using two main components: (i) the income impacts (i.e., marginal impacts from the distributional regression in Equation 2 multiplied with the frequency of occurrence) as the only source of income adjustment, and (ii) the equivalised household income from the nationally representative cross-sectional data of the EU-SILC from 2004 to 2022 as both the baseline (benchmark) income at the household level and as the indicator for calculating the relative poverty threshold at the country level.

By referencing both fixed and relative poverty thresholds to define a poor household in this analysis, we are able to isolate the poverty implications exclusively from the income impacts (fixed poverty threshold), and the income and inequality impacts (relative threshold) due to heatwaves, droughts, and CDHE. We acknowledge the sensitivity of the poverty incidence estimation to changes in inequality, which may be caused by multiple drivers in reality. In our projections, we identify changes in inequality resulting from the impacts of climate shocks on income across different income groups, for given initial income distributions (but disregarding other drivers of inequality).

We present a summary of poverty definitions that guide our estimation of historical counterfactual poverty incidence and future changes in poverty incidence in Table 2. The counterfactual income refers to the equivalised household income if no heatwaves, droughts, nor CDHE occurred in the same period (2004–2022). The projected income refers to the equivalised household income that is affected by future changes (2100) in the frequency of heatwaves, droughts, and CDHE, relative to the historical period (2004–2022). We present the results as poverty incidence or the percent share of the poor to total population, as well as in number of poor persons using the 2022 and 2100 population as reference years for the counterfactual and the future poverty estimates, respectively. The detailed steps of the calculation of poverty implications are found in Annex A.4.

4.3. Robustness checks and sensitivity analyses

We conducted several robustness checks and sensitivity analyses. We compare the results using IHS-transformed equivalised income against a natural log transformation. We rule out possible multicollinearity between heatwave and drought indicators. We tested our regressions with lagged covariants, use of alternative heat wave indicators (i.e., hot days with absolute thresholds and high UTCI) and replace heat wave-non dry days with heat wave-normal days to isolate any possible compound effect of heat wave-extreme wet days.¹⁵ The results of the robustness checks are found in Annex A.3.

5. Results and discussion

The results and discussion section is organised as follows: section 5.1 contains the discussion of the marginal impact of a heatwave day (*HWdry* and *HWnondry*) and a drought month directly coming from the regression results of Equation 1 covering all observations and Equation 2 subdividing the observations by income quintile; section 5.2 contains the historical average income impact, which combines our marginal estimates with average frequencies of heatwaves and droughts in years 2004–2022, and calculates the implication on poverty incidence due to the reduction in income and the change in the income structure due to disproportionate impacts by income quintile; section 5.3 contains our future risk estimates, where we calculate the reduction in income given future changes in the frequency of heatwave days and drought months, and the implications on future poverty incidence.

Unless otherwise specified, the uncertainty ranges presented in our results are from the confidence intervals of the estimated regression coefficients. While the future climate data also has its own uncertainty range, we only take the median value from the different global climate models in calculating future income and poverty impacts.

5.1. Marginal effects of heatwaves and droughts

5.1.1. Aggregate regression results

Our regression results (Table 3) show statistically significant reductions in household income for every additional heat wave day or drought month. The impacts of each variable on household income differ: a heatwave day coinciding with a drought month (*HWdry*) has an estimated impact of –2.9 percent [95 % CI: –2.9, –3.0], whereas a heatwave day without any compounding hazards has an estimated impact of only –0.7 percent [95 % CI: –0.7, –0.6]; a drought month has an estimated impact of –1.8 percent [95 % CI: –1.9, –1.7].

The gap between *HWdry* and *HWnondry* or a difference of 2.2 percentage points per heatwave day supports the hypothesis that compound extremes have amplified effects.

5.1.2. Distributional regression results

We use Equation 2 to test for the difference in responses of households by income quintile to the same frequency of heatwave and drought within a NUTS-1 region. Our results (see Table 4 and Fig. 1) show that the marginal impact of a drought month is statistically significant for the poorest quintile (–4.1 percent [–4.4, –3.8]) compared to the rest of the population (–1.8 percent to –1.1 percent range across income quintiles 2 to 5); whereas the impacts on *HWdry* (–3.6 percent to –2.5 percent across all income quintiles) and *HWnondry* (–1.6 percent to –0.8 percent across all income quintiles) remain relatively close. We note that the confidence interval range is larger for the poorest income quintile, suggesting a further disaggregation may be needed in future studies.

¹⁵ We have dropped heat wave-wet days from the regression due to the low number of observations.

Table 2
Summary of poverty definitions based on three poverty thresholds and equivalised household income adjustments.

	Relative poverty threshold: AROP60 based on actual EU-SILC equivalised income	Relative poverty threshold: AROP60 based on adjusted EU-SILC equivalised income	Fixed poverty threshold from Goedeme et al. (2022), with adjustments based on household size and inflation
Benchmark poverty	Actual equivalised income < actual AROP60 threshold	None.	Actual equivalised income < fixed threshold
Historical counterfactual poverty	Counterfactual equivalised income < AROP60 threshold in the Benchmark calculation	Counterfactual equivalised income < re-calculated AROP60 threshold based on the adjusted equivalised income	Counterfactual equivalised income < fixed threshold
Future poverty	Projected equivalised income in the 1.5 °C, 2 °C, and 2.7 °C scenarios < AROP60 threshold in the Benchmark calculation	Projected equivalised income in the 1.5 °C, 2 °C, and 2.7 °C scenarios < re-calculated AROP60 threshold based on the adjusted equivalised income in the 1.5 °C, 2 °C, and 2.7 °C scenarios	Projected equivalised income in the 1.5 °C, 2 °C, and 2.7 °C scenarios < fixed threshold

Table 3
Main Regression.

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>				
	ihs(Equivalised Income)				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
HW	-0.020*** (0.0003)		-0.014*** (0.0003)		
HWdry				-0.040*** (0.0004)	-0.029*** (0.0005)
HWnondry				-0.006*** (0.0003)	-0.007*** (0.0003)
Drought duration		-0.031*** (0.0004)	-0.026*** (0.0004)		-0.018*** (0.0004)
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Household FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year Fe	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	3,872,331	3,872,331	3,872,331	3,872,331	3,872,331
R ²	0.72	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.74
Adjusted R ²	0.72	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.74
F Statistic	23,147*** (df = 13; 3872298)	23,366*** (df = 13; 3872298)	21,879*** (df = 14; 3872297)	21,871*** (df = 14; 3872297)	20,542*** (df = 15; 3872296)

Note:
*p < 0.1.
**p < 0.05.
***p < 0.01.

Table 4
Distributional impacts.

	<i>Dependent variable:</i>				
	ihs(Equivalised Income by income quintile)				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
HWdry	-0.028*** (0.002)	-0.033*** (0.001)	-0.033*** (0.001)	-0.033*** (0.001)	-0.034*** (0.001)
HWnondry	-0.014*** (0.001)	-0.010*** (0.0004)	-0.008*** (0.0004)	-0.010*** (0.0004)	-0.010*** (0.0004)
DD	-0.041*** (0.001)	-0.014*** (0.001)	-0.012*** (0.001)	-0.013*** (0.001)	-0.017*** (0.001)
Control variables	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Household FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Year Fe	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Observations	839,300	793,744	748,656	731,409	759,222
R ²	0.021	0.084	0.083	0.079	0.067
Adjusted R ²	0.021	0.084	0.083	0.079	0.067
F Statistic	518*** (df = 34; 839259)	2,140*** (df = 34; 793703)	1,994*** (df = 34; 748615)	1,847*** (df = 34; 731369)	1,598*** (df = 34; 759181)

Note:
*p < 0.1.
**p < 0.05.
***p < 0.01.

Fig. 1. Estimated coefficients with 95% confidence interval.

5.2. Estimated historical impacts on household income and country-specific poverty incidence

5.2.1. Historical frequency of heatwaves and droughts

European regions experience heat waves and droughts in different frequencies, which partially determine the magnitude of impact on households. We present in Fig. 2 the average annual number of heat wave days and drought months from 2004 to 2022 by NUTS-1 region.

The average frequency of compound heat wave days or those coinciding with drought months are the highest in the regions of Central Hungary (HU1), Spain (i.e., Madrid (ES3), Central Spain (ES4), Northeastern Spain (ES2)), Slovakia (SK0), Corsica (FRM), Northern Serbia (RS1), and Central Italy (ITI). The average frequency of compound drought months or those coinciding with heat waves are the highest in the regions of Spain (i.e., Central Spain (ES4), Northeastern Spain (ES2), Southern Spain (ES6)), and Northwest Poland (PL9). Single heat wave

events or those that occur during non-drought months are most frequent in the regions of Malta (MT0), Slovakia (SIO), Northeast Italy (ITH), Croatia (HRO), and Southern Austria (AT2).

The average frequency of drought events are most frequent in the regions of Spain (i.e., Northeastern Spain (ES2), Madrid (ES3), Central Spain (ES4), Southern Spain (ES6), Canary Islands (ES7)), Italy (i.e., Southern Italy (ITF), Central Italy (ITI)), Germany (i.e., Berlin (DE3), Sachsen (DED), Brandenburg (DE4)).

5.2.2. Estimated historical income impacts of heatwaves and droughts

Combining the marginal impacts from Section 5.1 (Table 3, column 5) and the average frequency of HWdry, HWnondry, and DD from 2004 to 2022 by NUTS-1 region above, we estimate the average income impact from each hazard and the total impact from the summation of the three impacts (Fig. 3). Despite the lower frequency of HWdry compared to HWnondry (Fig. 2), the higher marginal effect of the former leads to a

Fig. 2. Average frequency of heatwaves-dry days (HWdry), heatwaves nondry days (HWnondry), and drought months (DD) from 2004 to 2022 by NUTS-1 region.

Fig. 3. Average estimated historical impact of heatwave-dry (HWdry), heatwave-nondry (HWnondry) and droughts (DD) on household income from 2004 to 2022 by NUTS-1 region. The income impacts are calculated by multiplying the marginal effect of a heatwave day or drought month to the average frequency of the hazards. The total income impact (Total) is a summation of the three impacts.

higher income impact (Fig. 3, two left-most maps). Accounting for the frequency of heat waves, HWdry (−1.4 percent) reduced household income by 0.8 percentage points more than single HWnondry (−0.6 percent).

Due to the high frequency of both heat waves (compound and single) and droughts, regions with the largest total income impacts are Madrid (ES3) with −9.7 percent [−10.1, −9.3], Central Hungary (HU1) with −9.4 percent [−9.8, −9.0], Central Spain (ES4) with −8.8 percent [−9.1, −8.4], Central Italy (ITI) with −8.5 percent [−8.9, −8.1], Northeastern Spain (ES2) with −7.7 percent [−8.0, −7.4], Northern Serbia (RS1) with −7.5 percent [−7.8, −7.2], Corsica (FRM) with −7.5 percent [−7.8, −7.2], and Slovakia (SK0) with −7.3 percent [−7.6, −6.9].

Averaging across the NUTS-1 regions, we find that the total income impact from heatwaves and droughts combined are the largest for the poorest income quintile (−7.3 percent [−8.0, −6.6]) compared to the rest of the population (ranging from −4.8 to −3.5 percent); or a total income impact gap of 2.7 percentage points [−3.2, −2.3] between the poorest and the richest quintile. Fig. 4 presents a map of the total estimated impact by income quintile.

5.2.3. Counterfactual poverty incidence

We calculated the country-specific poverty incidence using two poverty thresholds: the relative AROP60 threshold, and the fixed threshold from Goedeme et al. (2022). Because the AROP60 threshold is sensitive to the income distribution of each country per year, the calculation of a counterfactual household income, i.e., as if no heatwaves nor droughts occurred, changes the poverty line. In this regard, we effectively present three poverty thresholds: (a) AROP60 threshold

relative to the actual historical household income, (b) AROP60 threshold relative to the adjusted household income (factoring our impact estimates), and (c) the Goedeme et al. fixed threshold. We find value in including three different poverty thresholds due to the different messaging they convey: (a) AROP60 threshold relative to historical income estimates a fixed threshold for deprivation (“at-risk-of poverty” rather than poverty), (b) AROP60 threshold relative to a changing income structure is consistent to the poverty calculation of most countries in Europe, (c) the fixed threshold represent the minimum income a person needs to cover for basic needs (poverty, instead of “at-risk-of poverty”).

We estimate that the average at-risk-of-poverty incidence (AROP60 threshold using the adjusted income) increased by 1.1 percentage points [1.0, 1.2] or an equivalent of 5.6 million persons [5 million persons, 6.3 million persons] due to the occurrence of heatwaves and droughts in Europe from 2004 to 2022. Countries that have the largest percentage point increase in at-risk-of-poverty incidence from heat waves and droughts are Bulgaria (3.1 percentage points), Serbia (3 percentage points), UK (2.6 percentage points), Latvia (2.5 percentage points) and Greece (2.3 percentage points). In terms of population, the largest increase in at-risk-of-poverty are the UK (1.7 million persons), France (674 thousand persons), Italy (596 thousand persons), Spain (574 thousand persons), and Germany (555 thousand persons). As we have mentioned in the previous sections, the use of the relative poverty threshold may result in a reduction in at-risk-of-poverty incidence despite the reduction in income. This is the results of the poverty estimates for Portugal, Hungary, Slovakia, and Czechia.

To control for the movement of the poverty threshold when applying

Fig. 4. Total estimated income impacts from the combined effects (coefficient × frequency) of HWdry, HWnondry, and DD, averaged across years 2004–2022.

Average Poverty Impact of HW and DD, 2004-2022

Fig. 5. Comparison of actual poverty incidence (with heatwaves and droughts) and the counterfactual poverty incidence (without heatwaves and droughts) using different poverty thresholds by country and averaged over 2004-2022.

Fig. 6. Change in the frequency of HWdry, HWnondry, DD at 0.1 °C increments in global warming levels under RCP8.5, The line represent the mean value of all the median changes of HW or DD in all the NUTS-1 regions, the ribbons represent the lowest and highest median value of HW or DD among the NUTS-1 regions. The dotted vertical line represents the policy-relevant GWLs: +1.5 °C (Paris Agreement-consistent), +2.0 °C (NDC-consistent), +2.7 °C (current policies-consistent).

Fig. 7. Projected reduction in household income from the combined effects of HWdry, HWnondry and DD under global warming scenarios + 1.5 °C (left), +2°C (middle), and + 2.7 °C, relative to the reference period (+0.8 °C to + 1.4 °C).

the effects of heatwaves and droughty, we apply the AROP60 threshold fixed on actual income and the fixed threshold from Goedeme et al. On average from 2004 to 2022, the estimated increase in the number of the relatively deprived population is much higher than the increase in the absolute poor population. The at-risk-of-poverty incidence increased by 2 percentage points [1.9, 2.1] or an equivalent of 10.5 million persons, while the poverty incidence increased by 0.4 percentage points [0.3, 0.4] or an equivalent of 1.7 million persons. The countries with the highest poverty impact in percentage points remain the same for the at-risk-of-poverty measure. The use of the fixed threshold show that the

countries with the highest poverty impacts are Romania (2 percentage points), Bulgaria (1.9 percentage points), Latvia (1.3 percentage points), and Lithuania (1.1 percentage points) Fig. 5 presents the estimated poverty impacts due to heatwaves and droughts.

5.3. Future impacts

Climate projections indicate an expected increase in the frequency of compound dry-and-hot events and drought months as global warming levels increase, while there is a reduction in single heatwave events

Δ Poverty incidence due to HWdry, HWnondry, and DD

Fig. 8. Estimated change in the poverty incidence due to changes in heatwaves and droughts under different global warming scenarios (GWL + 1.5 °C, +2.0 °C, +2.7 °C) using relative (top and middle) and fixed (bottom) poverty thresholds.

(Fig. 6).

Combining these climate projections with the marginal income impact of HWdry, HWnondry, and DD (Table 3, column 5), we find an increase in the income impacts caused by HWdry and DD, and decrease in income impacts caused by HWnondry, relative to current climate (i.e., reference period of 1993–2023 corresponding to GWL of + 0.8 to + 1.4 °C).

Under a + 1.5 °C scenario, we estimate that total household income from the combined effects of HWdry, HWnondry, and DD is reduced by 7.4 percentage points, owing to the effects of HWdry (−5.2 percentage points) and DD (−2.3 percentage points), with a slight offset from HWnondry (+0.1 percentage points). Regions that have the highest income impact are Aegean Islands, Crete and Central Greece (EL4, EL6), South and South-west Romania (RO3, RO4), Northern and Eastern Bulgaria (BG3), and Cyprus (CY0).

The impacts on household income is significantly larger for higher levels of global warming. In comparison to the + 1.5 °C scenario, the + 2.0 °C scenario has an additional 4.4 percentage points reduction in household income (−11.8 percentage points), and the + 2.7 °C scenario has an additional 20 percentage points reduction in household income (−27.2 percentage points) (Fig. 7).

The change in the income structure from the income quintile-specific impact of future heatwaves and droughts lead to a change in the poverty incidence estimates (Fig. 8). In reference to the AROP60 threshold (adjusted income), we estimate an increase in 11 percentage points or 60 million persons in the at-risk-of-poverty incidence across Europe under the + 1.5 °C scenario by 2100, owing to the increase in HWdry, HWnondry, and DD. At-risk-of-poverty incidence increases further under a + 2 °C and + 2.7 °C with 13 percentage points or 69 million persons and 24 percentage points or 127 million persons, respectively.

6. Conclusions

Our analysis advances academic knowledge by reflecting three climate realities in impact modelling. First, there is a significantly higher impact on household welfare when compound extremes occur compared to the sum of single events, which provides a strong argument for including compound extremes in impact modelling to avoid underestimation of impacts and adaptation efforts. Second, given the same exposure to heat waves and droughts, we provide empirical evidence that the lowest income group bears the higher income loss, which effectively leads to higher income inequality. Third, the unequal distribution of income impacts result in an increase in the AROP rate, and, therefore, can act counterproductively to current efforts of reducing poverty to meet the 2030 European Pillars of Social Rights target.

Future climate projections show that heat and drought conditions will only get worse. Our analysis provides quantitative evidence of the magnitude of income and poverty impacts if we scale up climate mitigation measures to meet the commitments in the Paris Agreement. Failure to do so and to remain in the same level of climate action results in significantly higher income impacts and more people being at risk of poverty.

While our research has answered key questions on the impacts of compound extremes on household welfare, our results, as well as the limitations of our data, give birth to more questions for future research. The whole-of-economy approach of our analysis has provided the net

impact across many different sectors. A useful next step to this analysis is to determine the causal mechanisms and relative contributions of sectors (e.g., health, agriculture) to the overall income impact presented here, e.g., through path analyses, Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), mediation analyses, counterfactual decomposition or similar quantitative techniques that distinguish direct from indirect effects, and cascading impacts. Understanding this impact chain is crucial in providing a more targeted support for disaster risk reduction efforts, e.g., in identifying areas and timing of intervention to reduce cascading and system-wide impacts.

To further expand the knowledge on the socioeconomic impacts of compound extremes, we also suggest exploring the use of systemic risks frameworks to include a broader set of interlinked weather extremes, such as wildfire and flooding.

Data statement

All data used in this analysis are open source, except for the EU SILC data. The EU SILC data can be requested from the Eurostat by fulfilling the preconditions for accessing the microdata, and the submission of the research proposal (see <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/microdata/access>).

Author contributions

JRS contributed to all the components of the research. All authors were involved in the conceptualization, methodology, writing and review of the manuscript. FS and AZ contributed to the data management and programming.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Jessie Ruth Schleyen: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Fahad Saeed:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Anne Zimmer:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Tilman Brück:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix

A.1 Additional information on household data.

A.1.1 Available EU-SILC longitudinal data by country.

	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
EU Member States																		
Austria	AT																	
Belgium	BE																	
Bulgaria	BG																	
Cyprus	CY																	
Czech Republic	CZ																	
Germany	DE																	
Denmark	DK																	
Estonia	EE																	
Greece	EL																	
Spain	ES																	
Finland	FI																	
France	FR																	
Croatia	HR																	
Hungary	HU																	
Ireland	IE																	
Italy	IT																	
Lithuania	LT																	
Luxembourg	LU																	
Latvia	LV																	
Malta	MT																	
Netherlands	NL																	
Poland	PL																	
Portugal	PT																	
Romania	RO																	
Sweden	SE																	
Slovenia	SI																	
Slovakia	SK																	
United Kingdom	UK																	
Other countries																		
Switzerland	CH																	
Iceland	IS																	
Norway	NO																	
Serbia	RS																	
FYROM	MK																	
Montenegro	ME																	
Turkey	TR																	
35 countries		0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Annex 1: EU-SILC longitudinal data implementation by country (as of September 2023). Source: Eurostat.

A.1.2 Poverty thresholds.

Country	Average Poverty threshold			Average Poverty Incidence		
	AROP60 (actual income)	AROP60 (adjusted income)	Goedeme et al. Fixed	AROP60 (actual income)	AROP60 (adjusted income)	Goedeme et al. Fixed Threshold
AT	14,088	12,732	3055	14 %	10 %	1 %
BE	12,909	11,775	3107	14 %	9 %	1 %
BG	2180	1867	1417	21 %	14 %	10 %
CH	23,614	21,911	NA	16 %	11 %	NA
CY	9559	8719	2625	16 %	9 %	0 %
CZ	4931	4648	2010	9 %	6 %	1 %
DE	13,619	12,404	3102	15 %	7 %	1 %
DK	16,444	14,954	3851	12 %	8 %	1 %
EE	4715	4005	2144	20 %	12 %	4 %
EL	5601	4977	2535	20 %	14 %	4 %
ES	8533	7770	2698	20 %	14 %	3 %
FI	13,572	12,369	3466	13 %	8 %	0 %
FR	12,196	11,355	3041	13 %	9 %	0 %
HR	3998	3662	2080	20 %	13 %	5 %
HU	3080	2947	1647	13 %	9 %	2 %
IE	14,002	12,255	3351	16 %	9 %	1 %
IS	16,245	14,823	NA	10 %	7 %	NA
IT	9946	9126	2867	20 %	13 %	3 %
LT	3526	2969	1851	20 %	13 %	7 %
LU	21,348	19,511	3396	15 %	9 %	1 %
LV	3658	3027	2040	22 %	14 %	8 %
MT	8683	7775	NA	16 %	9 %	NA
NO	22,173	20,586	NA	12 %	8 %	NA
PL	3542	3178	1581	16 %	11 %	3 %
PT	6443	6026	2590	17 %	10 %	2 %
RO	1918	1632	1519	23 %	16 %	19 %
RS	1999	1792	NA	23 %	17 %	NA
SE	14,019	12,778	3326	15 %	10 %	2 %
SI	7615	7103	2375	13 %	9 %	0 %
SK	4056	4058	2014	12 %	8 %	3 %
UK	12,411	10,891	3220	17 %	12 %	1 %

Annex 2: Estimated poverty thresholds and corresponding poverty incidence averaged across years 2004–2023. AROP60 based on actual income is calculated using the equivalized household income (HX090) data from the cross-sectional EU-SILC; AROP60 based on adjusted income is calculated by, first, applying the estimated heatwave and drought coefficients to HX090 to assume no climate shock; then estimating the relative threshold; Goedeme et al. fixed threshold is based on the minimum country-specific income sufficient for food and housing for a family of 2 adults and 2 children.

All calculations of the thresholds are based on equivalized disposable income using the modified OECD scale and use the personal cross-sectional weight (RB050) to make the sample nationally representative.

A.1.3 Rotating panel of the EU-SILC and attrition rates.

We have an unbalanced panel from pooling together the longitudinal EU-SILC rotating panel from 2004 to 2022. The rotational panel design means that a fixed number of observations are kept, and in each year, a fourth of the sample is replaced by a new set of households that are retained in the panel for at least 4 years. In each survey year, there will be ¼ of the sample that are already in it's 4th survey wave (and will be dropped in the next year), ¼ in their 3rd survey wave (and will be retained for another year), ¼ in their 2nd survey wave (and will be retained for 2 more years), and ¼ in their 1st survey wave (and will be retained for the next three years). Due to planned attrition or the dropping of observations by rotational design, not all "drop-outs" in the sample, nor households with less than 4 years of observations contribute to the attrition rate.

The calculated attrition rate or the proportion of households leaving before completing 4 years ranged from 36 %-48 %, with mean 42 %. The calculation excludes the first 2 years (some households have a start year of 2003, and completed the 4 years in 2006) and the last 3 entry years (2020–2022), wherein households will still be retained for at least a year after to complete the 4 years. Annex 3 provides the attrition rate by entry year.

Annex 3: Attrition rates (top) and distribution of dropout hoshholds (bottom) across all NUTS regions by entry year from 2004 to 2022.

A.2 Additional information on the climate data.

A.2.1 Trends in historical and projected climate variables.

Annex 4: Maximum number of heatwave dry and heatwave nondry days, and drought months across all 105 NUTS-1 regions (92 EU + 12 UK + 1 Switzerland NUTS-1 regions).

Annex 5: Change in HWdry (top), HWnondry (middle), and DD (bottom) based on the projections from 4 GCMs at every 0.1 °C increase in global warming level using RCP8.5.

A.2.2 RCPs and GWLs.

Our selection of RCP 8.5 as the basis for our time-slicing approach is dependent on the range of global warming levels (GWLs) reached in the 4 global climate models (GCMs). In particular, we need the RCPs to reach GWLs of at least + 3°C relative to pre-industrial period to cover for all our policy-relevant scenarios (i.e., +1.5 °C, +2.0 °C and + 2.7 °C). Below, we see that RCP2.6 does not reach 2 °C in 3 out of 4 GCMs; RCP4.5 does not reach 3.0 °C in 2 out of 4 GCMs, and RCP6.0 does not reach 3 °C in one of 4 GCMs. Only RCP8.5 has information of up to 3.0 °C for all 4 GCMs.

Global Climate Model	Scenario	1.5 °C	2.0 °C	3.0 °C	4.0 °C
IPSL-CM5A-LR	rcp26	2025 (2010–2040)	not exceeded.	not exceeded.	not exceeded.
	rcp45	2025 (2010–2040)	2041 (2026–2056)	2111 (2096–2126)	not exceeded.
	rcp60	2026 (2011–2041)	2045 (2030–2060)	2083 (2068–2098)	not exceeded.
	rcp85	2022 (2007–2037)	2034 (2019–2049)	2054 (2039–2069)	2071 (2056–2086)
HADGEM2-ES	rcp26	2018 (2003–2033)	2036 (2021–2051)	not exceeded.	not exceeded.
	rcp45	2021 (2006–2036)	2037 (2022–2052)	2069 (2054–2084)	2288 (2273–2303)
	rcp60	2020 (2005–2035)	2039 (2024–2054)	2068 (2053–2083)	not exceeded.
	rcp85	2017 (2002–2032)	2029 (2014–2044)	2050 (2035–2065)	2068 (2053–2083)
MIROC5	rcp26	2036 (2021–2051)	not exceeded.	not exceeded.	not exceeded.
	rcp45	2033 (2018–2048)	2057 (2042–2072)	not exceeded.	not exceeded.
	rcp60	2044 (2029–2059)	2065 (2050–2080)	2091 (2076–2106)	not exceeded.
	rcp85	2027 (2012–2042)	2043 (2028–2058)	2067 (2052–2082)	2087 (2072–2102)
GFDL-ESM2M	rcp26	2089 (2074–2104)	not exceeded.	not exceeded.	not exceeded.
	rcp45	2049 (2034–2064)	2092 (2077–2107)	not exceeded.	not exceeded.
	rcp60	2056 (2041–2071)	2076 (2061–2091)	not exceeded.	not exceeded.
	rcp85	2036 (2021–2051)	2053 (2038–2068)	2082 (2067–2097)	not exceeded.

Annex 6: Range of global warming levels by Representative Concentration Pathways. Source: Climate Analytics Warming Attribution Calculator. <http://wlc.calc.climateanalytics.org/choices>. Accessed on October 5, 2025.

Scenario approximated	Model	GWL	Years that GWL was reached under RCP 8.5*
Reference period	IPSL-CM5A-LR	1.4 °C	2008
	HADGEM2-ES	0.9 °C	2008
	MIROC5	0.8 °C	2008
	GFDL-ESM2M	0.9 °C	2008
1.5 °C	IPSL-CM5A-LR	1.5 °C	2009–2011
	HADGEM2-ES	1.5 °C	2021–2022
	MIROC5	1.5 °C	2032–2035
	GFDL-ESM2M	1.5 °C	2034–2036
2.0 °C	IPSL-CM5A-LR	2.0 °C	2024–2027
	HADGEM2-ES	2.0 °C	2033–2035
	MIROC5	2.0 °C	2047–2049
	GFDL-ESM2M	2.0 °C	2050–2053
2.7 °C	IPSL-CM5A-LR	2.7 °C	2040–2041
	HADGEM2-ES	2.7 °C	2047–2048
	MIROC5	2.7 °C	2064–2065
	GFDL-ESM2M	12.7 °C	2072–2074

*31-year average around the indicated year.

Annex 7: Years when GWLs are reached under RCP 8.5.

A.3 Robustness and Sensitivity checks.

A.3.1 IHS vs LN.

We test our regression using a natural log transformation (ln) to the equivalised income and compare it against the inverse hyperbolic sine (ihs) used in the main analysis. We arrive at similar results: overlapping results for heatwave-dry days and droughts, and a slightly lower estimate of the impact of heatwave non-dry days to income using ihs. This difference is entirely attributable to the difference in the number of observations (3,872,331 observations using ihs and 3,856,973 observations using ln), because non-zero equivalised income is dropped when using ln. If we use the same observations, we arrive at the exact results using ihs and ln.

Annex 8: Estimated coefficients with 95 % confidence interval using an ihs and ln transformation of the equivalised household income using varying observations (top) and the same observations (i.e., keeping only non-zero, non-negative observations) (bottom).

	Main Regression				
	Dependent variable: ihs(Equivalised Income)				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Heatwave days (total)	-0.020*** (0.0003)		-0.014*** (0.0003)		
Drought duration		-0.031*** (0.0004)	-0.026*** (0.0004)		-0.018*** (0.0004)
Heatwave-dry days				-0.040*** (0.0004)	-0.029*** (0.0005)
Heatwave-nondry days				-0.006*** (0.0003)	-0.007*** (0.0003)
Observations	3,872,331	3,872,331	3,872,331	3,872,331	3,872,331
R ²	0.72	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.74
Adjusted R ²	0.72	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.74
F Statistic	23,147*** (df = 13; 3872298)	23,366*** (df = 13; 3872298)	21,879*** (df = 14; 3872297)	21,871*** (df = 14; 3872297)	20,542*** (df = 15; 3872296)

Note: *p < 0.1; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Main Regression

	Dependent variable:				
	ln(Equivalised Income)				
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
Heatwave days (total)	-0.021*** (0.0002)		-0.016*** (0.0002)		
Drought duration		-0.031*** (0.0003)	-0.025*** (0.0003)		-0.018*** (0.0003)
Heatwave-dry days				-0.040*** (0.0003)	-0.029*** (0.0003)
Heatwave-nondry days				-0.009*** (0.0002)	-0.009*** (0.0002)
Observations	3,856,973	3,856,973	3,856,973	3,856,973	3,856,973
R ²	0.141	0.142	0.143	0.143	0.144
Adjusted R ²	0.141	0.142	0.143	0.143	0.144
F Statistic	19,807*** (df = 32; 3856921)	19,920*** (df = 32; 3856921)	19,517*** (df = 33; 3856920)	19,490*** (df = 33; 3856920)	19,032*** (df = 34; 3856919)

Note: *p < 0.1; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Annex 9: Regression results using his (top) and ln (bottom).

A.3.2 Multicollinearity checks.

A.3.2.1 Variable Inflation Factor.. We estimate the variable inflation factor on the three climate variables and we find no multicollinearity issues (VIF < 5).

	Heatwave dry days (HWdry)	Heatwave non-dry days (HWnondry)	Drought month (DD)
VIF	1.418686	1.030624	1.412970

Annex 10: Variable Inflation Factor of HWdry, HWnondry, DD.

A.3.2.2 Pairwise correlation. We conduct a pairwise correlation between the three climate variables and their lags (up to 2 years of lags). Our results are consistent with the VIF test that we find no multicollinearity issues (|r| < 0.7).

Annex 10: Pairwise correlation of the climate variables and their lags up to 2 years.

A.3.3 Testing our disaggregation of heatwaves and other similar indicators.

	Dependent variable: ihs(Equivalised Income)
Heatwave-dry days	-0.037***(0.001)
Heatwave-normal days	-0.007***(0.0004)
Heatwave-wet days	-0.088***(0.003)
Drought duration	-0.024***(0.0005)
Observations	3,610,973
R ²	0.075
Adjusted R ²	0.075
F Statistic	18,271*** (df = 16; 3610939)

Note: *p < 0.1; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Annex 11: Robustness check using a disaggregation of heat wave-non dry days to normal and wet days.

Robustness.

	Dependent variable: ihs(Equivalised Income)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Heatwave-dry days (30 °C)	-0.003***(0.0001)			
Heatwave-nondry days (30 °C)	-0.018***(0.00005)			
Heatwave-dry days (35 °C)		-0.009***(0.0004)		
Heatwave-nondry days (35 °C)		-0.039***(0.0002)		
Heatwave-dry days (40 °C)			-0.340***(0.007)	
Heatwave-nondry days (40 °C)			-0.150***(0.004)	
High UTCI dry days				-0.001***(0.0001)
High UTCI nondry days				-0.012***(0.00003)
Drought duration	-0.037*** (0.001)	-0.034*** (0.0005)	-0.034 (0.0004)	-0.048 (0.001)

(continued on next page)

(continued)

		Dependent variable:		
		ihS(Equivalised Income)		
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Observations	3,610,973	3,610,973	3,610,973	3,610,973
R ²	0.106	0.081	0.074	0.104
Adjusted R ²	0.106	0.081	0.074	0.104
F Statistic (df = 15; 3610940)	28,678***	21,183 ***	19,351***	28,083***

Note: *p < 0.1; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

Annex 12: Robustness check using alternative measures of heat waves: absolute thresholds 30 °C, 35 °C, and 40 °C; and Universal Thermal Climate Index (UTCI) exceeding 32 °C.

A.3.4 Lagged covariates.

We tested the inclusion of lagged covariates in the regression equations. We find an optimal number of 2 years of lags. The inclusion of these lags do not drastically change our estimates in Table 2, given the weak correlation between the variables and their lags (see Annex 10).

A.3.4.1 Optimal number of lags based on the AIC/BIC criteria..

A.3.4.2 Regression results with the lagged covariates.

	Lagged Covariates			
	Dependent variable:			
	ln(Equivalised Income)			
	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
Heatwave-nondry days	-0.029***(0.0005) -0.007*** (0.0003)			(0.0005) -0.008*** (0.0003)
Drought duration	-0.018*** (0.0004)			-0.017*** (0.0004)
Heatwave-dry days (lag 1)		-0.025*** (0.0005)		-0.034*** (0.001)
Heatwave-nondry days (lag 1)		-0.012*** (0.0003)		-0.015*** (0.0004)
Drought duration (lag 1)		-0.022*** (0.0004)		-0.015*** (0.0005)
Heatwave-dry days (lag 2)			0.001*** (0.0005)	-0.002*** (0.0005)
Heatwave-nondry days (lag 2)			-0.004*** (0.0004)	-0.002*** (0.0004)
Drought duration (lag 2)			-0.055*** (0.0004)	-0.050*** (0.0004)
Observations	3,872,331	4,051,466	4,051,466	3,872,331
R ²	0.074	0.074	0.076	0.081
Adjusted R ²	0.074	0.074	0.076	0.081
F Statistic	20,542*** (df = 15; 3872296)	21,540*** (df = 15; 4051430)	22,208*** (df = 15; 4051430)	16,334 *** (df = 21; 3872290)

Note: *p < 0.1; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

A.4. Additional information on methodologies.

A.4.1. Calculating the impact on poverty incidence using the EU-SILC equivalised income and the estimated income impacts of heatwaves, droughts, and compound dry-and-hot events.

We take the following steps:

- i. Calculate the benchmark poverty incidence. We calculate the poverty incidence from the the equivalised household income based on two poverty thresholds: AROP60 threshold relative to actual income and the fixed poverty threshold from Goedeme et al. (2022). We average the annual poverty incidence across years 2004–2022 by country.
- ii. Calculate the historical counterfactual poverty incidence:
 - a. We adjust the equivalised household income to assume that no heatwaves nor droughts happened historically (counterfactual). This is calculated by adding back the income quintile-specific income impacts to the equivalised household income.
 - b. From the counterfactual equivalised household income, we calculate a third poverty threshold: AROP60 threshold relative to the adjusted income.
 - c. We estimate the counterfactual poverty incidence by calculating the share of households below the three poverty thresholds: AROP60 threshold relative to actual income, AROP60 relative to the adjusted income and the fixed poverty threshold. We average the annual counterfactual poverty incidence across years 2004–2022 by country.
 - d. We calculate the benchmark poverty incidence for the AROP60 relative to the adjusted income using the unadjusted equivalised income. We average the annual poverty incidence across years 2004–2022 by country.
 - e. We compare the average counterfactual poverty incidence with the average benchmark poverty incidence (step 1 and step 2.4) to get the change in the poverty incidence in percentage points due to the presence of heatwaves and droughts.
- iii. Calculate the future poverty incidence:
 - a. We adjust the equivalised household income by the projected income impact (i.e., marginal effects from Equation 2 multiplied by the projected frequency of heatwaves and droughts under future scenarios of global warming of + 1.5 °C, +2.0 °C and + 2.7 °C.)
 - b. From the future equivalised household income, we calculate the AROP60 threshold relative to the adjusted income.
 - c. We estimate the future poverty incidence and average the annual values (similar to step 2.3).
 - d. We calculate the benchmark poverty incidence for the AROP60 relative to the adjusted income using the unadjusted equivalised income.
 - e. We compare the average future poverty incidence with the average benchmark poverty incidence (step 1 and step 3.4) to get the change in the poverty incidence in percentage points due to the projected change in frequency of heatwaves and droughts under the different global warming scenarios.
- iv. Calculate the number of poor people based on the poverty incidence: To provide an equivalent poverty incidence in number of persons, we multiply the average country-specific counterfactual and projected poverty incidence to the national population projections from EUROPOP2023 for year 2022 and 2100, respectively.

Data availability

The authors do not have permission to share data.

References

- Ballester, J., Quijal-Zamorano, M., Méndez Turrubiates, R.F., et al., 2023. Heat-related mortality in Europe during the summer of 2022. *Nat. Med.* 29, 1857–1866. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41591-023-02419-z>.
- Beguera, S., Vicente Serrano, S. M., Reig-Gracia, F., & Latorre Garcés, B. (2024). SPEIbase v.2.10. Digital.CSIC. doi:10.20350/DIGITALCSIC/16497.
- Beguera, S., Vicente-Serrano, S.M., Reig, F., Latorre, B., 2014. Standardized precipitation evapotranspiration index (SPEI) revisited: parameter fitting, evapotranspiration models, tools, datasets and drought monitoring. *Int. J. Climatol.* 34, 3001–3302.
- Bellemare, M.F., Wichman, C.J., 2020. Elasticities and the inverse hyperbolic sine transformation. *Oxf. Bull. Econ. Stat.* 82 (1), 50–61. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obes.12325>.
- Borst, M. (2018). EU-SILC Tools: eusilpanel. First computational steps towards a cumulative sample based on the EUSILC longitudinal datasets. *GESIS Papers* 2018-11. GESIS – Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften. ISSN: 2364-3781 (Online). http://www.gesis.org/fileadmin/upload/dienstleistung/daten/amtl_mikrodaten/europ_microdata/EU-SILC/Tools/GESIS-Papers_2018-11.pdf.
- Borst, M., & Wirth, H. (2022). EU-SILC Tools: eusilpanel_2020 - first computational steps towards a cumulative sample based on the EU-SILC longitudinal datasets; Update. (GESIS Papers, 2022/10). Köln: GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften. doi:10.21241/ssoar.79965.
- Burbidge, J.B., Magee, L., Robb, A.L., 1988. Alternative transformations to handle extreme values of the dependent variable. *J. Am. Stat. Assoc.* 83 (401), 123–127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01621459.1988.10478575>.
- Carboni, O.A., 2012. An empirical investigation of the determinants of R&D cooperation: an application of the inverse hyperbolic sine transformation. *Res. Econ.* 66 (2), 131–141. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rje.2012.01.002>.

- Carter, M.R., Little, P.D., Mogues, T., Negatu, W., 2007. Poverty traps and natural disasters in Ethiopia and Honduras. *World Develop.* 35 (5), 835–856. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.worlddev.2006.09.010>. ISSN 0305-750X.
- Chen, J., Roth, J., 2024. Logs with zeros? Some problems and solutions. *Q. J. Econ.* 139 (2), 891–936. <https://doi.org/10.1093/qje/qjad054>.
- Chowdhury, S., Hänninen, R., Sofiev, M., Aunan, K., 2024. Fires as a source of annual ambient PM_{2.5} exposure and chronic health impacts in Europe. *Sci. Total Environ.* 922. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.171314>. ISSN 0048-9697.
- Climate Action Tracker (2024). 2100 Warming projections. November 2024. Available at: <https://climateactiontracker.org/global/temperatures/> Copyright © 2024 by Climate Analytics and NewClimate Institute. All rights reserved.
- Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), 2023: European State of the Climate 2022, Full report: climate.copernicus.eu/ESOTC/2022.
- Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S), Climate Data Store (CDS) (2024). Climate indicators for Europe from 1940 to 2100 derived from reanalysis and climate projections. <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/sis-ecde-climate-indicators?tab=overview>. Accessed on 30 September 2024.
- Devot, A., Royer, L., Arvis B., Deryng, D., Caron Giuffrè, E., Giraud, L., Ayrat, V., and Rouillard, J. (2023). Research for AGRI Committee – The impact of extreme climate events on agriculture production in the EU, European Parliament, Policy Department for Structural and Cohesion Policies, Brussels.
- Eiffe F. and Till M., 2014, The Longitudinal Component of EU-SILC: Still Underused?, Working Paper 1/2014, NetSILC2.
- Toreti, A., Bavera, D., Acosta Navarro, J., Jager, A., et al., 2022. Drought in Europe – European Commission: Joint Research Centre. Publications Office of the European Union. August 2022 – GDO analytical report.
- European Environment Agency (2024). European Climate Risk Assessment. EEA Report 01/2024. doi: 10.2800/8671471.
- European Forest Fire Information System (EFFIS) Statistics Portal. Accessed on 30 September 2024.
- European Union (2021). The European Pillar of Social Rights action plan. https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/economy-works-people/jobs-growth-and-investment/european-pillar-social-rights/european-pillar-social-rights-action-plan_en.
- EUROSTAT (a). EUROPOP2023 - Population projections at national level (2022-2100). Accessed on 30 September 2024.
- EUROSTAT (b). Glossary: At risk of poverty or social exclusion (AROPE). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/SEPDEF/cache/22724.pdf>. Accessed on 30 September 2024.
- EUROSTAT (c). Statistics explained: Living conditions in Europe - work intensity. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/SEPDEF/cache/67029.pdf>. Accessed on October 12, 2025.
- García-León, D., Casanueva, A., Standardi, G., et al., 2021. Current and projected regional economic impacts of heat waves in Europe. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 5807. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-26050-z>.
- Goedemé, Tim, and others (2018). 'What Does It Mean to Live on the Poverty Threshold? Lessons From Reference Budgets', in Bea Cantillon, Tim Goedemé, and John Hills (eds), Decent Incomes for All: Improving Policies in Europe (New York, 2019); online edn, Oxford Academic, 20 Dec.), doi:10.1093/oso/9780190849696.003.0002, accessed 29 Oct. 2024.
- Goedemé, T., Decerf, B., Van den Bosch, K., 2022. A new poverty indicator for Europe: the extended headcount ratio. *J. Eur. Soc. Policy* 32 (3), 287–301. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09589287221080414> (Original work published 2022).
- Gutiérrez-Nieto, B., Serrano-Cinca, C., Cuéllar-Fernández, B., et al., 2017. The poverty penalty and microcredit. *Soc. Indic. Res.* 133, 455–475. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11205-016-1368-4>.
- Hallegratte, S., Vogt-Schilb, A., Rozenberg, J., et al., 2020. From poverty to disaster and back: a review of the literature. *EconDisCliCha* 4, 223–247. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41885-020-00060-5>.
- Heal, G. and Park, J. (2013). Feeling the Heat: Temperature, Physiology & the Wealth of Nations. NBER Working Paper No. 19725. December 2013, Revised June 2014. JEL No. J01,Q54,Q56.
- ILO, (2019). Working on a warmer planet: The impact of heat stress on labour productivity and decent work. International Labour Office – Geneva, ILO. ISBN 978-92-2-132968-8 (web pdf).
- Jenkins, S.P., 2020. Perspectives on poverty in Europe. Following in Tony Atkinson's Footsteps. *Ital Econ J* 6, 129–155. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40797-019-00112-0>.
- Johnson, N.L., 1949. Systems of frequency curves generated by methods of translation. *Biometrika* 36 (1–2), 149–176. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biomet/36.1-2.149>.
- Kimmich, C., Weyerstraß, K., Czipionka, T., et al., 2025. Economic impact of labor productivity losses induced by heat stress: an agent-based macroeconomic approach. *Clim. Change* 178, 36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10584-025-03879-7>.
- Kjellstrom T, Holmer I, Lemke B. (2009). Workplace heat stress, health and productivity - an increasing challenge for low and middle-income countries during climate change. *Glob Health Action.* Nov 11;2. doi: 10.3402/gha.v2i0.2047. PMID: 20052422; PMCID: PMC2799237.
- Lange, B., Mack, A., Ponomarenko, V. (2021). Adding information on at-risk-of-poverty thresholds to longitudinal EU-SILC data (Version 2.00).
- Lin, Y., Jung, C., Hwang, B., Chen, C., 2025. Investigating wet-bulb globe temperature on heat-related illness in general population for alerting heat exposure: a time-stratified case-crossover study. *Urban Climate* 59, 102322. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.uclim.2025.102322>. ISSN 2212-0955.
- Mack, A. (2016). Data Handling in EU-SILC. GESIS Papers 2016-10. GESIS – Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften. ISSN: 2364-3781 (Online). https://www.gesis.org/fileadmin/upload/forschung/publikationen/gesis_reihen/gesis_papers/2016/GESIS-Papers_2016-10.pdf.
- Mckenzie, D. (2023). World Bank Blog: Interpreting treatment effects on an inverse hyperbolic sine outcome variable and alternatives <https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/impactevaluations/interpreting-treatment-effects-inverse-hyperbolic-sine-outcome-variable-and>. Accessed on October 14, 2025.
- Mitchell, D., AchutaRao, K., Allen, M., Bethke, I., Beyerle, U., Ciavarella, A., Forster, P. M., Fuglestedt, J., Gillett, N., Haustein, K., Ingram, W., Iversen, T., Kharin, V., Klingaman, N., Massey, N., Fischer, E., Schleussner, C.-F., Scinocca, J., Seland, Ø., Shiogama, H., Shuckburgh, E., Sparrow, S., Stone, D., Uhe, P., Wallom, D., Wehner, M., Zaaboul, R., 2017. Half a degree additional warming, prognosis and projected impacts (HAPPI): background and experimental design. *Geosci. Model Dev.* 10, 571–583. <https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-10-571-2017>.
- Mullahy, J., Norton, E.C., 2024. Why transform? The pitfalls of transformed regressions with a mass at zero. *Oxf. Bull. Econ. Stat.* 86 (2), 417–447. <https://doi.org/10.1111/obes.12583>.
- Naumann, G., Cammalleri, C., Mentaschi, L., et al., 2021. Increased economic drought impacts in Europe with anthropogenic warming. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 11, 485–491. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01044-3>.
- Norton, E.C., 2022. The inverse hyperbolic sine transformation and retransformed marginal effects. *Stata J.: Promoting Commun. Stat.* 22 (3), 702–712. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1536867X221124553> (Original work published 2022).
- Orlov, A., Sillmann, J., Aunan, K., Kjellstrom, T., Aaheim, A., 2020. Economic costs of heat-induced reductions in worker productivity due to global warming. *Global Environ. Change* 63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2020.102087>. ISSN 0959-3780.
- Osberghaus, D., Abeling, T., 2022. Heat vulnerability and adaptation of low-income households in Germany. *Global Environ. Change* 72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2021.102446>. ISSN 0959-3780.
- Parsons, K., 2002. *Human Thermal Environments: The Effects of Hot, Moderate, and Cold Environments on Human Health, Comfort, and Performance, Third Edition*, (3rd ed.). CRC Press. 10.1201/b16750.
- Parsons, K., 2019. *Human Heat Stress, (1st ed.)*. CRC Press. 10.1201/9780429020834.
- Rachunok, B., Fletcher, S., 2023. Socio-hydrological drought impacts on urban water affordability. *Nat. Water* 1, 83–94. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44221-022-00009-w>.
- Ravallion, M., 2017. A concave log-like transformation allowing non-positive values. *J. Econ. Behav. Organ.* 134, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.econlet.2017.09.019>.
- Rossi, L., Wens, M., De Moel, H., Cotti, D., Sabino Siemons, A., Toreti, A., Maetens, W., Masante, D., Van Loon, A., Hagenlocher, M., Rudari, R., Naumann, G., Meroni, M., Avanzi, F., Isabellon, M., Barbosa, P., 2023. European drought risk atlas, publications office of the European union. Luxembourg. <https://doi.org/10.2760/33211>. JRC135215.
- San-Miguel-Ayaz, J., Durrant, T., Boca, R., Maianti, P., Liberta, G., Oom, D., Branco, A., De Rigo, D., Suarez Moreno, M., Ferrari, D., Roglia, E., Scionti, N., Broglia, M., 2024. Advance report on forest fires in Europe, Middle East and North Africa 2023. *Pub. Off. Eur. Union, Luxembourg*. <https://doi.org/10.2760/74873>, JRC137375.
- Sedmeier, K., Feldmann, H., Schädler, G., 2018. Compound summer temperature and precipitation extremes over central Europe. *Theor. Appl. Climatol.* 131, 1493–1501. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00704-017-2061-5>.
- Seneviratne, S.I., X. Zhang, M. Adnan, W. Badi, C. Dereczynski, A. Di Luca, S. Ghosh, I. Iskandar, J. Kossin, S. Lewis, F. Otto, I. Pinto, M. Satoh, S.M. Vicente-Serrano, M. Wehner, and B. Zhou (2021): Weather and Climate Extreme Events in a Changing Climate. In *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis*. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Masson-Delmotte, V., P. Zhai, A. Pirani, S.L. Connors, C. Péan, S. Berger, N. Caud, Y. Chen, L. Goldfarb, M.I. Gomis, M. Huang, K. Leitzell, E. Lonnoy, J.B.R. Matthews, T.K. Maycock, T. Waterfield, O. Yelekçi, R. Yu, and B. Zhou (eds.)]. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, United Kingdom and New York, NY, USA, pp. 1513–1766, doi:10.1017/9781009157896.013.
- Suarez-Gutierrez, L., Müller, W.A., Marotzke, J., 2023. Extreme heat and drought typical of an end-of-century climate could occur over Europe soon and repeatedly. *Commun. Earth Environ.* 4, 415. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43247-023-01075-y>.
- Taylor, K.E., Stouffer, R.J., Meehl, G.A., 2012. An overview of CMIP5 and the experiment design. *Bull. Amer. Meteor. Soc.* 93, 485–498. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-11-00094.1>.
- Tripathy, K.P., Mishra, A.K., 2023. How unusual is the 2022 European compound drought and heat wave event? *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 50, e2022GL105453. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL105453>.
- United Nations (2015). Paris Agreement. https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/english_paris_agreement.pdf.
- Valenti, G., & Vona, F. (2025). Hot Wages: How Do Heat Waves Change the Earnings Distribution? FEEM Working Paper No. 31. November. doi: 10.22004/AG.ECON.348848.
- Vicedo-Cabrera, A.M., Scovronick, N., Sera, F., et al., 2021. The burden of heat-related mortality attributable to recent human-induced climate change. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 11, 492–500. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-021-01058-x>.
- Vicente-Serrano, S. M., Beguería, S., López-Moreno, J. I., Angulo, M., & El Kenawy, A. (2010). A New Global 0.5° Gridded Dataset (1901–2006) of a Multiscalar Drought Index: Comparison with Current Drought Index Datasets Based on the Palmer Drought Severity Index. *Journal of Hydrometeorology*. American Meteorological Society. doi: 10.1175/2010jhm1224.1.
- Whelan, C., and Maitre, B. (2008). Poverty in Ireland in Comparative European Perspective, ESRI Working Paper 265, Dublin: ESRI, <https://www.esri.ie/publications/poverty-in-ireland-in-comparative-european-perspective>.
- WHO (2021). Heat and health in the WHO European Region: updated evidence for effective prevention. Copenhagen: WHO Regional Office for Europe. License: CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 IGO.

- Wirth, H., Pforr, K., 2022. The European Union Statistics on Income and Living Conditions after 15 Years. *Eur. Sociol. Rev.* 38 (5), 832–848. <https://doi.org/10.1093/esr/jcac024>.
- Yin, J., Gentine, P., Slater, L., et al., 2023. Future socio-ecosystem productivity threatened by compound drought–heat wave events. *Nat. Sustain.* 6, 259–272. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-022-01024-1>.

- Zhao, et al., 2021. Global, regional, and national burden of mortality associated with non-optimal ambient temperatures from 2000 to 2019: a three-stage modelling study. *The Lancet Planetary Health* 5 (7) e415–e425.